

**Nomenclatural corrections to the “Lycaenidae part V” of the
“Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region” (Lepidoptera)**

Zsolt BÁLINT

*Hungarian Natural History Museum, Department of Zoology, Lepidoptera Collection,
H-1088 Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary. E-mail: balint.zsolt@nhmus.hu*

Abstract – It is remarked that the type species of *Bozania* Bálint, 2022 (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae), *Lycaena astorica* Tytler, 1926, is a junior primary homonym and a junior subjective synonym of *Lycaena astorica* Evans, 1925. *Tennentia* Bálint, 2022 is a junior homonym of *Tennentia* Humbert, 1862 (Mollusca), therefore *Johntennentia* nom. nov. is proposed as a replacement name for it. It is remarked that the author and year of description of the type species of *Tennentia* Bálint, 2022, *Lycaena martini* Allard, 1867, was erroneously cited as “Oberthür, 1861” in the original publication.

Key words – homonym, replacement name, synonym, type species

INTRODUCTION

The 24th volume of the series “Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region” (BÁLINT 2022) was published on 31 January 2022. The book treated some genera of Polyommata (Lycaenidae: Polyommatinae: Polyommatini), one of the most diverse groups of butterflies in the Northern Hemisphere (TALAVERA *et al.* 2012, 2021). In BÁLINT (2022) three new genus-group names were established. Mistakes regarding two of these were discovered when the volume had already been in press, and they are corrected in the present correspondence.

NOMENCLATURAL CORRECTIONS

Bozania Bálint, 2022
(BÁLINT 2022: 11)

The nominal species *Lycaena astorica* Tytler, 1926 was designated as the type species of *Bozania* Bálint, 2022. It is, however, a junior primary homonym of *Lycaena astorica* Evans, 1925 (BÁLINT 1999), and a junior subjective synonym of the latter species, erroneously claimed to be its objective synonym by BÁLINT (1999).

Tennentia Bálint, 2022
(BÁLINT 2022: 13)

Tennentia Bálint, 2022 is a junior homonym of *Tennentia* Humbert, 1862 (currently a junior synonym of *Mariaella* Gray, 1855; Mollusca: Ariophantidae) (MOLLUSCABASE 2021). Therefore, the replacement name ***Johntennentia* nom. nov.** is proposed for *Tennentia* Bálint, 2022. The author and year of description of the type species of *Tennentia* Bálint, 2022, *Lycaena martini* Allard, 1867, was erroneously cited as “Oberthür, 1861” in the original publication (BÁLINT 2022) due to an inadvertent error.

*

Acknowledgements – Thanks are due to Mrs Giancristoforo Bozano (Milano, Italy), Stanislaw Kolb (Nizhny Novgorod, Russia), and Gerardo Lamas (Lima, Peru) for their comments.

REFERENCES

- BÁLINT Zs. 1999: Annotated list of type specimens of *Polyommatus* sensu Eliot of the Natural History Museum. – *Neue entomologische Nachrichten* **46**: 1–89.
- BÁLINT Zs. 2022: Lycaenidae part V. Subfamily Polyommatinae. Tribe Polyommatini (partim). – In: BOZANO G. C. (ed.): *Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region*. Omnes Artes, Milano, 106 pp.
- MOLLUSCABASE 2021: *Tennentia* Humbert, 1862. Available from: <https://www.molluscabase.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=999441> (accessed 29 April 2022)

- TALAVERA G., LUKHTANOV V. A., PIERCE N. E. & VILA R. 2012: Establishing criteria for higher-level classification using molecular data: the systematics of *Polyommatus* blue butterflies (Lepidoptera, Lycaenidae). – *Cladistics* 29(2): 166–192. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-0031.2012.00421.x>
- TALAVERA G., LUKHTANOV V. A., PIERCE N. E. & VILA R. 2021: DNA barcodes combined with multilocus data of representative taxa can generate reliable higher-level phylogenies. – *Systematic Biology* 70(2): 382–395. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syab038>